

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Can be darkish or mild brown (cinnamon), generally even white. Not at all times black in shade. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected under the U.S. □□ Size: Adults [ikea panda teddy](#) weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six ft in length. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are a few of the perfect at climbing trees. Their comparatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb bushes for protection, food, and even hibernation. The majority of their food plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Food plan: Their assorted weight loss plan offers them the flexibility to stay in a big range of habitats. In addition they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They are the almost definitely bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and reduced habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the name of the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals comparable to elk and moose. Their colour varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft lengthy, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three ft. □□ Food regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than these discovered in the Rocky Mountains attributable to a richer eating regimen. Annually there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Known for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are liable for probably the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are virtually as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1, four hundred pounds, 8 ft long, and 4 feet tall at the shoulder. □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight loss plan is much like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, on account of more plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to become their own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social construction which results in less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. Resulting from their isolation, there is just one attack on humans every different 12 months. Largest species of bear on this planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food plan is usually made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white however is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary within the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 ft tall. They are a threatened species resulting from loss of habitat from climate change. Despite their enormous dimension polar bears might be quick, sustaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slim head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Eating regimen: Their diet consists principally of animals, particularly seals which they'll smell from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears may be extremely dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Attacks are rare because of the distant nature of their habitat. Known for its cream coloration chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Simple to tame and often widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered susceptible. □□ Dimension: One of the smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food regimen: Relying on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on humans are increasing

as folks encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered solely in China. 99% of its eating regimen is bamboo. In fact, the second particular person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Solely 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are thought of a vulnerable species. □□ Measurement: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and may be over 4 feet tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at start. It additionally has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in gentle brown and white. □□ Weight loss program: In contrast to different bears the panda's diet is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The large panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them regular: they poop over forty instances a day! □□ Harmful? Assaults are rare however dangerous, on condition that pandas have one in every of the highest bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is unsure but thought of susceptible and on the decline resulting from loss of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and different physique components utilized in conventional medicines. □□ Dimension: They stand only 39 to fifty five inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising solar. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Solar bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." The truth is, they have an incredibly lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? As a consequence of its shy nature, assaults are rare. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of lower than 20,000, they are thought of weak. □□ Size: They are 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they are straightforward to tell apart from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very quick and can out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from timber. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their massive curved claws. □□ Weight loss plan: Their food plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They're probably the most aggressive bears, with essentially the most assaults on humans, largely resulting from shock encounters. They blow the mud around with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and don't mix well with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at each other when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's final short-confronted bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that look like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are discovered in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Measurement: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last quick-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Features: The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that generally appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. □□ Food regimen: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a weight-reduction plan consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, but they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Dwelling in remote mountains, these shy bears stands out as the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however haven't been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA assessments were unable to find out what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas usually are not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in area. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their own family that are nearer cousins with skunks and

raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is nearby, through which case you want to be additional vigilant. Listed here are a couple of tips you should use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are right here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you'll have great intentions, a bear is more likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Secure YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** If you happen to see a bear, do not try to strategy or feed it. This includes food, but also your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you select, ensure that it's a minimum of 200 feet away out of your tent so you don't entice bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** For those who meet a bear, don't run. Try to make your self look as huge as doable, waving your arms above your head. You can too extend a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Struggle Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play dead. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet long, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the most important bear by each dimension and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat again with all your power and hope that it will again down. Which bear is essentially the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for essentially the most attacks. When in bear country, it's at all times sensible to carry bear spray. It's effectively deserved, especially when cubs are round. Annually there are approximately forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to death. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome reputation. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on common there is only one assault per 12 months. In terms of raw bite power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When utilizing the bite force quotient (bite power relative to measurement), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he turned an icon and to this day is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has impressed numerous through-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free way of life. He additionally is perhaps the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would go to at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near the place he was from. Chris also wrote *Methods to Hike the Appalachian Trail*. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and the way-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

